

Supplementary for

Morpho-functional traits of the coral *Stylophora pistillata* enhance light capture for photosynthesis at mesophotic depths

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Text S1

To systematically test the role of different coral morphologies on coral light transport, we designed a large number of simulations with varying morphologies and optical properties. As our primary aim was to understand the role of differences in morphology between shallow vs mesophotic morphotypes, independent of other differences between these groups that can affect light propagation (e.g., changes in algal density and/or skeletal scattering) we ran simulations under identical optical properties for shallow and mesophotic morphotypes. Additionally, to understand whether differences in light propagation between morphotypes remain true for various optical properties, we systematically tested scenarios where we varied tissue pigmentation, tissue scattering, skeletal scattering, and skeletal absorption one at a time. ‘Default’ optical properties were chosen based on previous studies (Kramer et al. 2022, Jacques et al. 2019) and assumes high skeletal scattering ($\mu_s' \text{ skeleton} = 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), intermediate tissue scattering ($\mu_s' \text{ tissue} = 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as well as moderate tissue pigmentation/absorption ($\mu_a \text{ tissue} = 1.18 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and low skeletal absorption ($\mu_a \text{ skeleton} = 0.01 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). We then systematically varied one optical property at a time. Simulation scenario (2) reduced pigmentation - uses a tissue absorption coefficient that is about half of the default value, (3) Enhanced pigmentation - uses x10 enhanced $\mu_a \text{ tissue}$, (4) low $\mu_s' \text{ tissue}$ - uses x10 lowered $\mu_s' \text{ tissue}$, (5) High $\mu_a \text{ skeleton}$ - uses high skeletal absorption, and (6) low $\mu_s' \text{ skeleton}$ - uses x5 lowered $\mu_s' \text{ skeleton}$. While these additional simulations are by no means thought to be exhaustive, they should be regarded as representative of different optical properties this coral could have in nature resulting from adaptation to different environments.

The scattering anisotropy and the phase function were assumed to be constant (g-value = 0.9 for both tissue and skeleton; see Wangpraseurt et al. (2016)). The Monte Carlo model assumes the Henyey-Greenstein (HG) phase function which has been routinely used for various types of human tissue and in a few coral studies. A recent study used inverse Optical Coherence

Tomography and suggested that the use of the HG phase function might be inappropriate for some corals and some regions of corals (specifically coral tissue⁴). However, so far it is unknown whether this might also be the case for different corals, such as *Stylophora Pistillata* used in this study.

References

1. Kramer, N. *et al.* Efficient light-harvesting of mesophotic corals is facilitated by coral optical traits. *Functional Ecology* **36**, 406–418 (2022).
2. Jacques, S. L., Wangpraseurt, D. & Köhl, M. Optical Properties of Living Corals Determined With Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy. *Front Mar Sci* **6**, 1–9 (2019).
3. Wangpraseurt, D., Jacques, S. L., Petrie, T., & Köhl, M. (2016). Monte Carlo Modeling of Photon Propagation Reveals Highly Scattering Coral Tissue. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 7(September), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01404>

Table S1. Summary table of the average morphological traits (in mm) and photosynthetic light response (P - E) parameters used in the light simulation models (resolution = 0.005 mm/pixel).

Trait	Shallow	Mesophotic
<i>Morphology</i>		
Tissue thickness	0.12	0.07
Calyx diameter	0.98	0.62
Corallite marginal spacing	0.50	0.80
Theca height	1.20	0.84
Columella height	0.64	0.61
Septal length	0.20	0.13
Septal width	0.12	0.08
Coenosteum spine length	0.16	0.10
Coenosteum spine width	0.10	0.08
Coenosteum spine spacing	0.15	0.13
<i>P-E</i>		
Maximum photosynthetic rate (P_{max})	22.2	19.6
Saturation irradiance (E_k)	120.0	64.4
Optimum irradiance (E_{opt})	326.2	175.1

Table S2. The surface area (mm²), surface rugosity (real surface area divided by geometric surface area divided; more complex < 1), and tissue volume (mm³) for shallow and mesophotic architectures for different morphological scenarios.

	Morphotype	<i>In-situ</i>	No calyx	No columella	No coenosteal spines	No septae	Corallite spacing exchanged	Corallite diameter exchanged	Corallite height exchanged
Surface area	Shallow	8.93	3.72	8.79	7.87	6.44	10.58	6.40	7.18
(mm ²)	Mesophotic	5.27	2.80	5.15	4.59	4.16	4.25	7.52	6.38
Surface	Shallow	4.08	1.70	4.01	3.59	2.94	3.34	5.10	3.28
rugosity	Mesophotic	2.62	1.39	2.55	2.28	2.06	3.38	2.37	3.17
Tissue volume	Shallow	0.92	0.22	0.96	0.95	1.09	1.02	0.31	0.68
(mm ³)	Mesophotic	0.31	0.12	0.32	0.32	0.36	0.26	0.73	0.39

Table S3. Summary table of the light simulation scenarios containing the architectural (Table S1; in mm) and optical parameters (Kramer et al. 2021; per cm^{-1}) used in each scenario. These parameters were applied in the models of (a) shallow and (b) mesophotic morphotypes under both low-light ($45 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and high-low ($750 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) conditions. Values in bold indicate the changed value for simulation from default settings.

Simulation scenario	a. Shallow morphotype								
	Calyx (mm)	Theca (mm)	Columella (mm)	Spines (mm)	corallite spacing (mm)	μ_a tissue	μ_a skeleton	μ_s' tissue	μ_s' skeleton
Default	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
Reduced tissue absorption	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	0.66	10	0.01	15
Enhanced (x10) tissue absorption	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	11.8	10	0.01	15
Reduced tissue scattering	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	0.1	0.01	15
High skeleton absorption	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.47	15
Reduced skeleton scattering	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	3
No calyx	0	0	0	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
No columella	0.98	1.2	0	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
No coenosteal spines	0.98	1.2	0.64	0	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange calyx diameter	0.62	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange calyx height	0.98	0.84	0.64	0.16	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange corallite spacing	0.98	1.2	0.64	0.16	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15

Simulation scenario	b. Mesophotic morphotype								
	Calyx (mm)	Theca (mm)	Columella (mm)	Spines (mm)	corallite spacing (mm)	μ_a tissue	μ_a skeleton	μ_s' tissue	μ_s' skeleton
Default	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
Reduced tissue absorption	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	0.66	10	0.01	15
Enhanced (x10) tissue absorption	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	11.8	10	0.01	15
Reduced tissue scattering	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	0.1	0.01	15
High skeleton absorption	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.47	15
Reduced skeleton scattering	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	3
No calyx	0	0	0	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
No columella	0.62	0.84	0	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
No coenosteal spines	0.62	0.84	0.61	0	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange calyx diameter	0.98	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange calyx height	0.62	1.2	0.61	0.1	0.8	1.18	10	0.01	15
Exchange corallite spacing	0.62	0.84	0.61	0.1	0.5	1.18	10	0.01	15

Figure S1. A correlation matrix based on Pearson's correlation coefficients between skeletal traits. Color scale denotes positive (*blue*) to negative (*red*) correlation coefficients. Significance corresponds to circle size and is shown as p-values within the circles.

Figure S2. The total photosynthetic scores (summed by tissue pixel) of different bio-optical and morphological simulation scenarios under (a) high-light (equivalent to 5 m; $750 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and (b) low-light (equivalent to 50 m; $45 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) conditions. Color denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*) and the ambient photosynthetic performance (*P-E*) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down). Filled triangles and dashed vertical lines represent the scores for settings as found in nature for shallow and mesophotic corals.

Figure S3. “Default settings” scenario (see Table S3). Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance (*P-E*) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S4. "Enhanced (x10) tissue absorption" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) μmol photons $m^{-2} s^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as $W m^{-2}$; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S5. "Reduced tissue absorption" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S6. "Reduced tissue scattering" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S7. "High skeleton absorption" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu mol photons m^{-2} s^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as $W m^{-2}$; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S8. “Low skeleton scattering” scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S9. "No corallite" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y - z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S10. "No columella" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance (P-E) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S11. "No coenosteal spines" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S12. “No septae” scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y - z axes) under light intensities of **(c-f)** 750 (high light) and **(g-j)** 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. **(a-b)** Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. **(c-j)** Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S13. “Swap calyx diameter” scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y - z axes) under light intensities of **(c-f)** 750 (high light) and **(g-j)** 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. **(a-b)** Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. **(c-j)** Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance ($P-E$) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S14. “Swap calyx height” scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y - z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance (P - E) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S15. "Swap corallite spacing" scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; "fire" color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score ("rainbow" color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: blue; mesophotic: red), and the ambient photosynthetic performance (P-E) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S16. “Reduced tissue scattering without columella” scenario. Light propagation simulations shown in 2D (y-z axes) under light intensities of (c-f) 750 (high light) and (g-j) 45 (low light) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (a-b) Relative fluence rates (delivered as W m^{-2} ; “fire” color gradient) with contour indicating the surface boundaries. (c-j) Photosynthetic score (“rainbow” color gradient) on the tissue layers. Triangle color above the figures denotes the morphotype (shallow: *blue*; mesophotic: *red*), and the ambient photosynthetic performance (*P-E*) is represented by shape (shallow: triangle point up; mesophotic: triangle point down).

Figure S17. Relative electron transport rate (rETR) versus irradiance (photosynthetically active radiation, PAR, 400–700 nm) curves for shallow (*blue*) and mesophotic (*red*) corals ($n = 6$). Error bars are SE.